

ACUTE ADHESIVE INTESTINAL OBSTRUCTION

Kamalova Sayyora Yakubjonovna¹

¹Assistant of the Department of Surgical Diseases and General Surgery,
Termez branch of the Tashkent Medical Academy.

Abdiyev Otabek Choriyevich²

²Regional Multidisciplinary Medical Center Surgeon

Xonov Sadridin Shoho'jayevich³

³Assistant of the Department of Surgical Diseases and General Surgery,
Termez branch of the Tashkent Medical Academy.

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Annotation: This article describes acute adhesive intestinal obstruction, its causes, development paths, diagnosis and modern methods of treatment.

Key words: intestinal obstruction, peritonitis, appendicular abscess, plain radiography, abdominal cavity.

Adhesive intestinal obstruction is a violation of the movement of food masses and digestive juices through the intestines, associated with the formation of adhesions. This is a fairly common pathology, which is a serious problem in surgery and gastroenterology, it occupies approximately 30-40% of all types of intestinal obstruction. It occurs equally often in both men and women, regardless of age. The relevance of the disease has recently increased significantly due to the increase in the number and volume of surgical interventions on the abdominal organs. According to many authors, approximately 40% of all operations are accompanied by the appearance of adhesions, while up to 60% of all laparotomies are performed for adhesive intestinal obstruction.

The reasons for the formation of adhesions can be traumatic injuries, bleeding into the abdominal cavity, ischemia of the gastrointestinal tract, foreign bodies, negative effects of toxins, purulent processes in the abdominal cavity (peritonitis, appendicular abscess, etc.), surgical interventions, during which the peritoneum dries out (most often these are appendectomies, operations for the pathology of the uterus and appendages), genetic predisposition.

The mechanism of formation of adhesions is explained by the disorder of the processes of resorption of inflammatory elements and their replacement by connective tissue. It is known that the peritoneum in response to injury and any impact produces exudate, which has sticky properties. Connective tissue fibers are formed from its cells, fibrin gradually falls out, which should be absorbed at the end of the healing process. If this does not happen, it sprouts with collagen and elastic fibers, vessels - this is how adhesions are formed.

Adhesive intestinal obstruction is divided into three types: obstructive, strangulation and combined (with signs of a mechanical and dynamic type: it usually develops when adhesions form between the inflammatory focus in the abdominal cavity and intestinal loops). They also distinguish superacute, acute and chronic forms of pathology, which differ in the rate of development, severity and severity of symptoms.

The obstructive type of pathology is caused by compression of the intestinal loops by adhesions, but at the same time they do not violate its blood supply and innervation. Pain sensations appear suddenly, they are associated with increased peristalsis and are paroxysmal in nature. The time of occurrence of vomiting with impurities of bile and greenery depends on the level of the obstruction: the higher the obstruction, the faster the vomiting develops. The patient is determined by a uniform bloating, the discharge of gases is disturbed, and constipation occurs. The doctor can see intestinal motility through the abdominal wall and determine the increase in noise.

Strangulation is characterized by compression of the mesentery of the intestine and is complicated by necrosis of the digestive tract. Clinical signs develop acutely and suddenly: there is severe pain in the abdomen without a clear localization, pallor of the skin, the patient cannot find a comfortable position, refuses to eat. Intestinal necrosis may cause symptoms to subside, but only for a short time. Vomiting without impurities, it has a reflex character and is caused by trauma to the mesentery. Gradually, there is a delay in the passage of gases and stools. Signs of toxicosis are growing rapidly (increased heart rate, blood pressure drops, weakness, dizziness, dehydration, etc.). Initially, the abdomen is soft, but painful cider causes tension in the abdominal muscles. Peristalsis is invisible to the naked eye.

Adhesive intestinal obstruction, as a rule, is a complication of surgical procedures, while it can develop at different times. In patients with severe peritonitis, pathology is recorded in the first days after surgery. The severe condition of the patients and the pronounced signs of the underlying pathology mask the symptoms of obstruction. Patients are disturbed by periodic cramping pains, vomiting. Asymmetrical bloating develops gradually. Palpation is painful, touching the muscles causes increased pain. The chair is missing.

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